

Review of Path Planning, Search, and Area Coverage Methods for Multi-Agent Systems with Emphasis on Mathematical and Ergodic Approaches

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Abstract This paper provides a structured overview of path planning, search, and area coverage problems, with a focus on multi-agent autonomous systems and mathematically grounded approaches. The evolution of path planning is reviewed, from classical graph-based, sampling-based, and artificial potential field methods to recent centralized and decentralized multi-agent pathfinding (MAPF) strategies. Search methods are examined from early Koopman models to adaptive real-time algorithms, while area coverage approaches are discussed from distributed Voronoi-based strategies to modern ergodic methods such as SMC and HEDAC. The interconnections between path planning, search, and coverage are highlighted, and a comparative analysis of the reviewed methods is presented, emphasizing their advantages, limitations, and suitability for operation in uncertain environments with limited resources.	Article history Received: 27.02.2026. Revised: 1.4.2026. Accepted: 2.4.2026. Keywords Path Planning, Search, Area Coverage, Multi-Agent Systems, Mathematical Modeling.
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1 Introduction

With the rapid advancement of technology, and especially robotics and autonomous systems, the problem of multi-agent search and continuous surveillance of a given area has emerged as one of the most significant research challenges. In such systems, agents may be unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), autonomous ground vehicles (UGVs), autonomous surface vehicles (USVs), or autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs), equipped with various sensors and communication modules. Their coordinated cooperation enables more efficient execution of complex tasks compared to the operation of a single agent, particularly in spatially large, dynamic, or hard-to-access environments.

Multi-agent search and coverage problems have an exceptionally wide range of applications. In security and military contexts, they are used for border surveillance, protection of critical infrastructure, and real-time threat detection. In civilian applications, they include urban patrol, traffic monitoring, disaster management, and searching collapsed buildings or

wildfire areas for survivors. In maritime and aviation contexts, they are used for search-and-rescue operations, detecting aircraft wreckage, or monitoring maritime surfaces. Furthermore, in agriculture and ecology, they are used for precision crop spraying, vegetation monitoring, pollution detection, or wildlife population surveillance.

The key advantage of multi-agent systems lies in their ability to operate in parallel and distribute tasks, significantly reducing mission execution time and increasing system reliability. However, such systems simultaneously introduce a number of theoretical and practical challenges. It is necessary to ensure efficient path planning, mutual collision avoidance, optimal resource allocation, robustness to communication constraints, and adaptation to uncertain and dynamic environmental conditions. For this reason, the problems of path planning, area coverage, and area search form the foundation of research in the field of coordinated control of multiple autonomous agents.

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Although these problems are often formulated separately, they are strongly interconnected. Effective area search depends on the quality of path planning, while successful space coverage is a prerequisite for reliable target detection. In complex and uncertain environments, the boundaries between these problems become increasingly blurred, leading to the development of integrated approaches that combine elements of all three domains.

This paper presents a structured review of path planning, search, and area coverage methods for multi-agent systems, with particular emphasis on mathematically grounded and ergodic approaches, emphasizing their theoretical foundations, interconnections, and key properties in uncertain and dynamic environments.

2 Path Planning, Coverage, and Search of a Given Area

The problems of searching an area with the goal of finding static or moving targets are closely related to area coverage problems and agent path planning, as all of these problems share common challenges such as obstacle and collision avoidance, efficient use of resources, and operation in uncertain or dynamic environments. In the following, each problem is explained individually, and a review of the relevant literature is provided for each. Through the presentation of existing solutions and approaches, it will become evident that, despite different formulations, these problems are often solved using related methods and techniques.

2.1 Agent Path Planning Problem

Path planning is one of the fundamental tasks in the field of autonomous mobile systems, robotics, and control theory. The goal is to find a sequence of positions or states that guide an agent (e.g., a mobile robot, drone, or autonomous vehicle) from a starting point to a target point while respecting environmental constraints and avoiding obstacles. It is important to emphasize that path planning does not necessarily have to be an optimization problem. In its basic formulation, it is posed as a feasibility problem, where it is sufficient to find any collision-

free path connecting the start and goal points. Optimality, in terms of minimal distance, time, or energy consumption, is an additional requirement that depends on the specific application. This distinction is clearly emphasized by LaValle in [1], where motion planning in its simplest form is defined as a feasibility problem, while in its more complex form it becomes an optimization problem. A similar approach is adopted by Choset et al. in [2].

Over the years, numerous algorithms and approaches for single-agent path planning have been developed, differing in the way the space is modeled, how solutions are generated, and in computational complexity.

Path planning methods can also be broadly classified into classical and heuristic approaches, depending on the way solutions are generated and the level of optimality guarantees. Classical methods include graph-based algorithms, sampling-based approaches, and artificial potential field methods. These approaches are typically well-understood and, in some cases, provide guarantees of completeness and optimality.

Graph-based algorithms model the space as a graph, where graph vertices represent possible agent positions and edges represent allowable motions between them. Depth-First Search (DFS) [3] and Breadth-First Search (BFS) [4] are among the earliest graph-based approaches to path planning. These algorithms enable systematic exploration of the graph and finding paths between vertices, with BFS guaranteeing the shortest path in terms of the minimum number of edges. Other well-known algorithms in this category include Dijkstra's algorithm for finding the shortest path from a source vertex to all other vertices in a graph with non-negative edge weights, described by Edsger W. Dijkstra in [5], and the A* algorithm, presented in [6], which combines characteristics of Dijkstra's algorithm and breadth-first search by using a heuristic function to guide the search toward the goal, making it efficient in many applications. A limitation of these methods is that their

applicability may decrease in high-dimensional or continuous spaces due to the need for discretization, which can significantly increase computational cost.

Sampling-based methods are particularly useful in high-dimensional or complex configuration spaces where explicit representation of all possible states is not practical. They avoid exhaustive search for the entire space by randomly sampling configurations and attempting to connect them with valid paths. Two prominent algorithms in this category are the Probabilistic Roadmap Method (PRM) presented in [7], and the Rapidly-exploring Random Tree (RRT) algorithm presented and described in [8], [9]. One drawback of basic sampling-based variants is the lack of guaranteed optimality, while their performance can also be sensitive to sampling density and parameter selection.

Due to their simplicity, artificial potential field (APF) methods are often used for motion planning, search, and area coverage in both static and dynamic environments. Khatib presented such a method in 1986 in [10], with the goal of planning collision-free motion for a robotic manipulator based on artificial potential fields. The basic idea is to assign an attractive potential to the goal and a repulsive potential to obstacles in the robot's environment. The combination of these fields results in an artificial potential field in which the robot is treated as a particle moving under its influence. Improvements of the APF method followed in [11], [12], [13]. Despite their conceptual simplicity and computational efficiency, artificial potential field methods are prone to local minima and oscillatory behavior, which can prevent agents from reaching their goals in complex environments. As a result, numerous extensions of APF methods have been proposed, including harmonic and Laplacian potential fields, evolutionary and optimization-based variants, and hybrid approaches combining artificial potential fields with global planning methods, which over time have been further refined to provide nearly optimal, smooth trajectories and enable application to dynamic multi-agent search scenarios aimed at finding specific

targets. By combining APF with genetic algorithms, the Evolutionary Artificial Potential Fields (EAPF) method was developed in [14] for real-time robot path planning, while [15] presented a hybrid method combining APF and Simulated Annealing for motion planning of a team of multi-jointed robotic snakes. More advanced approaches using Laplace's equation to model the potential field for path planning were applied in [16], [17], [18], [19]. At the same time, these methods remain susceptible to local minima and oscillatory behavior, which may limit their reliability in complex or cluttered environments.

In contrast, heuristic and nature-inspired methods rely on stochastic search and optimization strategies to explore the solution space. These approaches are typically inspired by natural processes and collective behaviors observed in biological systems. Among the most prominent techniques in this category are the Genetic Algorithm (GA) [20], Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) [21], Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) [22], Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) [23], and Bacterial Foraging Optimization (BFO) [24].

Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) is inspired by the collective behavior of swarms, where a set of particles moves through the search space by iteratively updating their positions based on both their individual experience and the best solution found by the swarm. Ant Colony Optimization (ACO), on the other hand, is based on the foraging behavior of ants, where artificial agents construct solutions by following and reinforcing pheromone trails that encode the quality of previously discovered paths.

Although these methods are primarily general-purpose optimization techniques, they have also been adapted for both single-agent and multi-agent path planning problems (Multi-Agent Path Finding – MAPF problem). Their flexibility and ability to handle complex, high-dimensional, and dynamic environments make them particularly suitable for scenarios where classical methods may struggle.

The MAPF problem involves coordinating the motion of multiple agents in a shared space to avoid collisions

and optimize collective movement. Different approaches to solving this problem can be classified as centralized or decentralized.

Centralized approaches rely on a central system that possesses complete information about all agents and their goals. This system plans paths for all agents simultaneously, considering mutual interactions and potential conflicts. Examples include the Conflict-Based Search (CBS) algorithm presented in [27], [28], which decomposes the MAPF problem into many constrained single-agent path planning problems, as well as its improvements [29], [30].

Decentralized approaches allow each agent to make decisions independently based on local information and limited communication with other agents. These approaches are more scalable and robust to individual agent failures but may struggle to achieve globally optimal solutions due to limited situational awareness. In [31], a decentralized multi-agent algorithm, Decentralized Multi-Agent Rapidly-exploring Random Tree (DMA-RRT), is described, enabling efficient path planning in complex environments while ensuring collision avoidance.

Table 1 Comparison of path planning approaches

Category	Examples	Advantages	Limitations	Applications
Classical methods (primarily single-agent)	Graph-based (DFS, BFS, Dijkstra, A*)	Complete, optimal (A*, Dijkstra), well-understood	Poor scalability in high-dimensional spaces requires discretization	Grid-based navigation, shortest path problems
	Sampling-based (PRM, RRT)	Suitable for high-dimensional spaces, flexible	No guaranteed optimality (basic versions), parameter sensitivity	Robotics, motion planning
	Artificial Potential Fields	Simple, computationally efficient, and real-time capable	Local minima, oscillations, lack of global guarantees	Obstacle avoidance, real-time navigation
Heuristic/nature-inspired methods	GA, PSO, ACO, ABC, BFO	Flexible, suitable for complex and high-dimensional environments, no explicit modeling required	No guarantees of optimality or completeness, parameter sensitivity, and possible slow convergence	Complex optimization problems, dynamic environments, both single- and multi-agent planning
Multi-Agent Path Finding (MAPF)	Centralized	High-quality solutions can be optimal	Computationally demanding, limited scalability	Coordinated multi-agent systems
	Decentralized	Robust, low communication requirements	Limited global coordination, possible suboptimality	Swarm robotics, distributed systems
Learning-based approaches	Reinforcement Learning	Adaptive, handles complex and dynamic environments, and can be generalized	Limited theoretical guarantees, training cost, and sim-to-real gap	Autonomous systems, dynamic and uncertain environments, single- and multi-agent
Hybrid approaches	Classical + RL / Heuristic combinations (e.g., A* + RL, ORCA-A*)	Combines the strengths of multiple paradigms, improved robustness, and performance	Increased complexity, integration challenges	Complex real-world systems requiring both guarantees and adaptability, single- and multi-agent
Coverage/search objectives	Ergodic methods (SMC, HEDAC)	Incorporates spatial distributions, suitable for search and coverage	Computational cost, parameter tuning	Area coverage, search, surveillance, single- and multi-agent settings

In [32], the WSCaS (Walk, Stop, Count, and Swap) decentralized multi-agent path planning algorithm is described, which guarantees near-optimal solutions on grid maps without narrow passages. Centralized approaches explicitly coordinate all agents and can effectively prevent conflicts such as multiple agents occupying the same location. However, this requires solving the problem of coupled scheduling in space and time for all agents simultaneously, which can become computationally demanding as the number of agents increases. In contrast, decentralized approaches resolve conflicts locally, reducing the computational cost but potentially leading to less coordinated behavior. More recent studies highlight their effectiveness, especially when combined with hybrid or learning-based strategies [25], [26].

The choice between centralized and decentralized approaches depends on application-specific factors, including the number of agents, environment complexity, available communication resources, and scalability requirements.

In addition to the previously described approaches, recent research has increasingly explored learning-based methods, particularly those based on reinforcement learning (RL), including PRIMAL, described in [33], ORCA described in [34], MAP3F described in [35], and the hybrid ORCA-A* method described in [36]. While RL-based approaches demonstrate strong performance in simulation and high adaptability to complex environments, they often lack formal guarantees of optimality, completeness, and safety, particularly under partial observability and communication constraints. In addition, training requirements, sim-to-real transfer issues, and sensitivity to reward design can present challenges that may limit their deployment in safety-critical or large-scale real-world applications. Hybrid approaches combining classical planning algorithms (e.g., A*) with learning-based components have also been explored to balance theoretical guarantees and adaptability [37], [38].

Path planning can also be formulated as an ergodic search problem, where paths are planned such that trajectory density matches a prescribed probability density of target occurrence, as demonstrated in [39], [40]. Such formulations provide a unified perspective

that connects path planning, area coverage, and search, particularly in scenarios involving uncertainty and spatial distributions of information. These approaches can be applied in both single-agent and multi-agent settings, including MAPF scenarios.

As summarized in Table 1, the reviewed approaches exhibit complementary strengths and limitations. Classical graph-based methods can provide completeness and, in some cases, optimality guarantees, but may scale poorly in high-dimensional or continuous environments due to discretization requirements. Sampling-based methods improve scalability and are well-suited to complex configuration spaces, although basic variants typically do not guarantee optimality and may require parameter tuning. Artificial potential field methods offer computational efficiency and real-time applicability but may suffer from local minima and oscillatory behavior in complex environments.

Heuristic and nature-inspired methods provide high flexibility and are particularly effective in complex, high-dimensional, and dynamic environments, as they do not require an explicit representation of the entire search space. However, they generally lack guarantees on optimality and completeness and may be sensitive to parameter selection and convergence issues.

In multi-agent settings, MAPF approaches introduce additional coordination challenges, where centralized methods can achieve high-quality or optimal solutions at the cost of increased computational complexity, whereas decentralized methods improve scalability and robustness but may lead to suboptimal global behavior. Learning-based approaches further enhance adaptability and performance in complex and uncertain environments but often require substantial training data and lack formal guarantees, with additional challenges related to generalization and sim-to-real transfer.

Hybrid approaches combine elements of classical, heuristic, and learning-based methods to leverage their complementary strengths, often achieving a balance between solution quality, computational efficiency, and adaptability. Finally, ergodic approaches, such as SMC and HEDAC, provide a

principled framework for coverage and search by incorporating spatial probability distributions, making them particularly suitable for uncertain and dynamic environments.

2.2 Area Search Problem for Static or Moving Targets

In contrast to classical path planning approaches, which primarily focus on determining a path between known locations, search and exploration methods address the problem of locating a target under uncertainty.

Bernard Koopman, while investigating strategies for detecting German submarines during World War II, laid the foundations of optimal area search through a series of papers [41], [42], [43], [44] and the book [45]. He formulated the problem as determining how to best conduct a search for a given object when total search resources (e.g., time, sensors, or human resources) are limited and the only known information is the probability that the object is located at specific positions.

This problem evolved into a broader search theory, whose main objective is to find the most efficient allocation of limited resources to detect a target with an unknown exact location. In [46] and [47], the conditions and assumptions of such search processes are described, assuming that the searcher operates under uncertain conditions and gradually acquires information about the target location during the search.

The amount of information available during the search is modeled using a detection function, which describes the probability of detecting the target as a function of expended effort (e.g., sensor coverage). The most commonly used detection function is the so-called Koopman detection function, presented in [43], which has the form of an exponential function:

$$\beta(c) = 1 - e^{-ck} \quad \text{Eq 1}$$

where c denotes cumulative search effort, and k is a constant depending on sensor effectiveness and search conditions. This function is strictly increasing and concave, reflecting diminishing returns in detection probability as effort increases. This model

describes the relationship between expended effort and detection probability; however, it may not accurately represent more complex sensing scenarios where detection does not follow a simple exponential behavior.

Research has shown that search planning can be implemented in two main ways: first, by constructing a complete search plan in advance, reducing the problem to classical path planning and is possible when the environment and target location are known in advance; and second, by continuously updating the search plan during execution based on new information from the environment (adaptive or real-time search).

Early work in search theory focused primarily on the first approach and can be viewed as an optimal path-planning problem, in which the main task was the optimal distribution of search effort among a team of agents assumed to be sufficiently capable of achieving the goal. These models typically rely on strong assumptions, such as accurate prior knowledge of the target distribution and well-characterized sensing models, which limit their applicability in real-world scenarios. Classical Koopman-based models provide a strong theoretical framework for optimal search; however, their practical use remains constrained by these assumptions.

Some of the notable contributors in this area include Stone, who in [48] presented an algorithm for optimal search planning in discrete time and space, as well as Brown [49], Washburn [50], and Eagle [51], who extended Stone's algorithm with Koopman detection functions to moving-target scenarios. The incorporation of Koopman detection functions represents a significant improvement, as it accounts for imperfect detection and sensor limitations; however, it still assumes that detection characteristics are known and stationary over time. Later, Singh and Krishnamurthy [52] extended this approach to non-Koopman detection functions and infinite-horizon search scenarios. While more general, such formulations increase computational requirements. These extensions improved the applicability of classical search models, especially for moving targets and long-duration searches.

In parallel with discrete-domain search, the problem of searching for a target in continuous time and space was also studied. Hellman formulated the general target motion equation and derived the necessary conditions for optimal search in [53], and provided a comprehensive overview of models and results in [54]. Significant contributions were also made by Lukka [55], who constrained the search problem based on the motion capabilities of the agent and target, and by Ohsumi [56], who analyzed optimal search methods and derived optimal search paths that maximize detection probability in finite time in specific cases. Continuous formulations enable more realistic modeling of motion and sensing, but they often lead to analytically intractable problems and require numerical approximation methods that may be sensitive to discretization and parameter choices.

Adaptive area search methods have been developed especially in recent years, as they allow agents to dynamically decide which part of the area to search next, improving efficiency and adaptability to uncertain or changing conditions. Such approaches have been shown to achieve approximately optimal search trajectories and high detection probabilities. These methods highlight the importance of real-time decision-making in complex environments. Unlike classical approaches, adaptive methods can incorporate sensor feedback and update belief distributions online, making them more suitable for partially observable and non-stationary scenarios. However, they often require increased computational resources and may depend on heuristic or approximate solutions.

For example, Kagan, Goren, and Ben-Gal [57] presented an adaptive area search algorithm for static and moving targets in discrete time and space using non-Koopman detection functions. This algorithm was later adapted to Koopman detection functions in [58], [59]. In parallel, Israel, Khmelnsky, and Kagan presented an adaptive search algorithm for moving targets based on Ohsumi's model in [60].

In [61], the impact of cooperation and information exchange on search duration and detection accuracy is evaluated, using information fusion strategies for data sharing among agents. Cooperation and information sharing can improve search performance, although they may introduce additional communication and coordination requirements. This highlights a key trade-off between performance and system complexity, as increased cooperation often leads to higher communication overhead and potential scalability issues.

In [62], a cooperative multi-agent search method in an uncertain environment is described, using a decentralized approach based on sensor measurements and continuous data acquisition during motion. Decentralized approaches reduce coordination requirements, but may lead to less efficient global behavior. In [63], the authors presented an ergodic-theory-based search algorithm adapted for complex geometries and uncertainties in ocean search, demonstrating its effectiveness through simulation of the search for aircraft MH370. This work uses a modified version of the Dynamic Spectral Multiscale Coverage (DSMC) algorithm presented in [40], which is an adaptation of the Spectral Multiscale Coverage (SMC) algorithm presented in [64] for dynamically changing environments. Ergodic methods link search strategies with spatial probability distributions, enabling a balance between exploration and coverage, although they may require careful parameter tuning and can be computationally demanding. Additionally, their performance can be sensitive to the accuracy of the underlying probability distribution, which may be difficult to estimate in practice.

To provide a structured overview of the discussed search approaches, Table 2 summarizes their main characteristics, highlighting differences in their assumptions, adaptability, and coordination requirements.

Table 2 Comparison of area search methods

Method Type	Examples	Advantages	Limitations	Applications
Classical Search	Koopman [41-45], Stone [48]	Strong theoretical foundation, optimal resource allocation under known assumptions	Requires prior knowledge of the target distribution and sensing model	Military search, structured environments
Adaptive Search	Kagan et al. [57-59], Israel et al. [60]	Updates search strategy during execution, improves detection under uncertainty	Increased computational cost may rely on approximate solutions	Dynamic environments, moving targets
Multi-Agent Search	Cooperative and decentralized approaches [61], [62]	Improve performance through cooperation and information sharing	Communication overhead, coordination complexity	Multi-agent systems, distributed search
Ergodic Search	DSMC/SMC [63], HEDAC [39]	Incorporates spatial distributions, balances exploration and coverage	Computationally demanding, sensitive to distribution accuracy	Ocean search, uncertain environments

A related class of problems is studied through maze navigation tasks, which provide controlled environments for evaluating search strategies. In such settings, agents must explore unknown environments or locate targets under limited prior knowledge. Classical approaches include graph-based methods such as BFS [65], DFS-based methods [3], and A* [6], as well as maze-specific strategies such as flood-fill and wall-following [66]. These methods are computationally efficient and easy to implement, but they are primarily designed for single-agent scenarios and typically assume static environments without explicitly modeling uncertainty.

Some of these methods have later been extended to multi-agent settings. In particular, a modification of Tarry's algorithm for multi-agent exploration was presented in [67], where the authors address the problem of finding an exit in unknown perfect mazes. Further improvements were introduced in [68], where a multi-agent search algorithm capable of handling different types of mazes was proposed, including additional mechanisms for collision avoidance between agents. Despite these extensions, most existing approaches are still primarily designed for single-agent exploration, and relatively few works address the multi-agent case [69].

More recent approaches include reinforcement learning methods such as Deep Q-Networks (DQN)

[70], where agents learn navigation policies through interaction with the environment and improve their performance based on accumulated experience. In contrast to heuristic methods, this approach does not rely on predefined rules but adapts to unknown maze structures over time. Bio-inspired methods, such as ant colony optimization [71] have also been proposed, where multiple agents cooperate through indirect communication mechanisms (e.g., pheromone-based models) to optimize search time. In this approach, after locating the target, additional path-planning methods, such as Dijkstra's algorithm, are used to efficiently reach it.

In parallel, ergodic-based approaches such as HEDAC [72] provide a different perspective by linking agent motion with spatial probability distributions, enabling systematic exploration of the environment. Such methods aim to balance coverage and target localization and have been extended to more complex scenarios, including multi-agent exploration of unknown environments.

Figure 1 illustrates a 50×50 maze search conducted by 50 agents coordinated through the HEDAC algorithm. It is assumed that the agents have no a priori information about the maze structure or the target location. During movement, each agent can observe only its neighboring cells, while exchanging information with other agents about discovered and previously visited cells. In this way, the agents

Figure 1 HEDAC maze exploration in a 50×50 maze under unknown environment conditions.

operate on a domain that expands over time. It can be observed that 50 agents can complete a search of the maze in 101 steps, achieving efficient coverage of the environment while searching for the target. This process is further illustrated in Figure 2, which shows the percentage of visited cells over time steps during the search.

Overall, classical search methods provide strong theoretical guarantees and structured optimal solutions under well-defined assumptions, but their reliance on prior knowledge and offline optimization limits their effectiveness in dynamic and uncertain environments.

In contrast, adaptive and real-time approaches offer greater flexibility and robustness by incorporating feedback and updating strategies online, at the

expense of increased computational complexity and reliance on approximate solutions.

Despite significant progress, most existing approaches remain predominantly focused on single-agent scenarios, while multi-agent search in unknown environments is still relatively underexplored. Approaches based on alternative paradigms, such as ergodic exploration, provide a promising direction for achieving more efficient coverage and coordination in such settings.

2.3 Area Coverage Problem

The area coverage problem is one of the key challenges in the field of autonomous mobile agents. It is closely related to the previously described area search problem, as both aim to efficiently move agents through space to cover an entire area in the

Figure 2 Percentage of visited cells as a function of time steps

minimal time. Area coverage also plays a crucial role in continuous domain monitoring tasks, where it is important to maintain agent presence in specific regions over time, as well as in tasks such as spraying, cleaning, or mapping. Due to its wide applicability, the area coverage problem is relevant in fields including military, agriculture, ecology, and rescue systems.

In [73], three versions of the Spanning Tree Covering (STC) area coverage algorithm are described. This algorithm is based on decomposing the area to be covered into simple cells and constructing a spanning tree that represents adjacency between these cells. The robot systematically traverses the entire area by following the branches of this tree, ensuring complete coverage without unnecessary overlapping or backtracking.

In [74], an algorithm for distributed and adaptive control of groups of autonomous vehicles is presented, where each vehicle acts as a mobile adjustable sensor. By using Voronoi diagrams and gradient-based methods, optimal area coverage is achieved.

In [75], the authors presented an adaptive multi-robot path planning algorithm for covering unknown areas. The goal is for robots to efficiently explore and cover the entire space while dealing with uncertainty regarding the environment configuration. This problem is similar to target search with unknown location, as in both cases, agents must explore unknown areas while coping with uncertainty and the need for adaptive planning. Strategies developed for path planning and coverage can therefore be adapted to efficiently search for and localize unknown targets.

The Spectral Multiscale Coverage (SMC) method described in [64] enables centralized control of multi-agent systems, ensuring that agents spend time in regions of the domain proportional to the probability that a target is located there, corresponding to ergodic exploration of the domain. The algorithm uses Fourier transforms, which can be computationally demanding and may lead to instability in some cases. SMC prioritizes global coverage over local coverage, which is not always desirable, particularly when local search is a priority.

Additionally, repeated coverage of the same areas may result in suboptimal agent behavior. As previously noted, the SMC method has been adapted for dynamically changing domains (DSMC) in [40] and later further improved for ocean surface search in [63].

In the Heat Equation Driven Area Coverage (HEDAC) method, first introduced in [39], the coverage problem is formulated through a coverage density that is approximated using radial basis functions (RBFs). The motion of agents is driven by the gradient of a potential field obtained by solving a stationary heat-distribution equation, enabling efficient and continuous redistribution of agents across the domain. The source term of this equation depends on the difference between the achieved and the target coverage density in insufficiently covered regions of the domain, thereby emphasizing areas of interest.

Moreover, by appropriately tuning the parameters of the governing equation, the method can be made to favor local or more global coverage enhancement. In this way, the HEDAC method is flexible and adaptable to a wide range of applications. Consequently, this approach more effectively targets under-visited regions and provides explicit control over whether to prioritize local or global coverage than the SMC method.

Since the resulting potential field in the HEDAC method governs the agents' movement, a clear connection to APF approaches is evident. In area coverage problems, a coverage density is predefined, describing how intensively or frequently each part of the area is covered by the system's actions. If this density is interpreted as the probability of a target's presence, the coverage problem can also be viewed as an area search problem, where resources are allocated proportionally to that probability. Moreover, area coverage methods can be applied in other scenarios, such as spraying an area, where the coverage density corresponds to the desired spray density or distribution of the substance over the area. The tests reported in [39] illustrate the evolution of agent trajectories with respect to the prescribed target coverage density, along with the corresponding coverage error obtained using both SMC and HEDAC approaches. As time progresses, the trajectories

Figure 3 Agent trajectories after 1000 time steps obtained using the HEDAC method, with the gray-shaded region indicating areas of higher target coverage density. Reproduced from [39]

Figure 4 Agent trajectories after 1000 time steps obtained using the SMC method, with the gray-shaded region indicating areas of higher target coverage density. Reproduced from [39]

increasingly concentrate in regions associated with higher target density, while the coverage error gradually decreases, indicating convergence toward ergodic behavior. The results demonstrate that the HEDAC method achieves a faster reduction in coverage error than SMC, with similar performance trends observed across the reported experiments. One example of the test from [39] is shown in Figures 3, 4, and 5.

From these results, it can be observed that the HEDAC method is more successful, as the agent trajectories more closely approximate the prescribed target coverage density and the coverage error decreases faster than with the SMC method.

Figure 3 shows the results obtained using the HEDAC method after 1000 steps. Figure 4 presents the corresponding results for the SMC method, while Figure 5 illustrates the evolution of the coverage (ergodic) error over time for both approaches.

Figures 6 and 7 illustrate an example of applying the HEDAC method to area coverage using 10 agents. The environment model is presented in Figure 6, where a relatively complex domain is considered, characterized by an almost uniform target coverage density across most of the space and the presence of

Figure 5 Evolution of the coverage error over time for SMC and HEDAC methods. Reproduced from [39]

Figure 6 Spatial target coverage density

Figure 7 Trajectories of 10 agents after 1000 time steps using the HEDAC method, with each agent's trajectory shown in a distinct color

four obstacles that agents must avoid. Figure 7 shows that the density of agent trajectories over time closely matches the prescribed target coverage density, indicating that the system exhibits ergodic behavior. Such results highlight the effectiveness of ergodic coverage approaches in complex environments and motivate their broader application in related domains.

Recent studies linking area coverage with path planning and search include variants of the HEDAC and SMC algorithms. In [63], an SMC-based ergodic search algorithm was applied to ocean search operations and demonstrated its effectiveness through simulations of the search for aircraft MH370.

The HEDAC method has been adapted for a range of tasks involving coordinated coverage. For example, the autonomous control of non-uniform spraying using multiple UAVs [76] showed that HEDAC-controlled UAVs outperform conventional path planning approaches. Similar principles have been applied to robotic drawing [77], and to UAV search missions [78], [79], incorporating obstacle avoidance, irregular domains, non-radial sensor footprints, and heterogeneous swarms.

HEDAC has also been used for autonomous 3D visual inspection with multiple UAVs [80], demonstrating flexibility in planning paths that ensure thorough coverage while enabling real-time detection of relevant features.

Beyond these practical applications, recent studies have also focused on establishing the theoretical foundations of ergodic approaches. In particular, the convergence of the Spectral Multiscale Coverage (SMC) approach has been analyzed in recent work by Lukhozi [81], where it was established in the sense of measures in negative Sobolev spaces, providing theoretical support for long-term ergodic coverage. Given the connection between SMC and HEDAC methods [39], these results further support the theoretical foundation of the HEDAC approach.

Further developments of the HEDAC method have been reported in [72], focusing on improving computational efficiency and numerical methods for potential field computation, as well as extending the applicability to continuous and discrete domains, including scenarios with initially unknown environments.

These studies help address key challenges related to execution time, path accuracy, and coverage quality, particularly in real-time and complex environments. They further confirm the potential of ergodic approaches as an effective tool for surveillance and search in increasingly demanding real-world applications.

Such interest in ergodic approaches is to be expected, given the rapid development of autonomous agents that are increasingly employed for surveillance, exploration, and complex tasks in challenging environments. In this regard, methods such as HEDAC and SMC provide a natural and mathematically grounded framework for efficient resource allocation, robust area coverage, and adaptation to uncertain and dynamic conditions.

To provide a clearer comparison of the coverage approaches discussed, Table 3 summarizes their main characteristics, highlighting how ergodic methods extend classical and adaptive approaches by incorporating spatial information via a prescribed target distribution.

Table 3 Comparison of area coverage methods

Method Type	Examples	Advantages	Limitations	Applications
Classical Coverage	STC [73]	Ensures complete coverage with minimal overlap, simple, and computationally efficient	Limited adaptability to complex or unknown environments	Cleaning, mapping, and area traversal
Adaptive Coverage	Voronoi-based and adaptive multi-robot methods[74], [75]	Adapts to the environment, supports distributed control, effective in unknown areas	Requires coordination, sensitive to parameters, and higher complexity	Environmental monitoring, exploration, and target localization
Ergodic Coverage	SMC [64], HEDAC [39]	Explicitly incorporates a prescribed spatial distribution, ensuring ergodic coverage and balancing exploration and exploitation, with a strong theoretical foundation	Computationally demanding, requires parameter tuning, implementation complexity	Search, surveillance, inspection, ocean search

3 Future Directions and Open Challenges

Despite significant progress in the development of coverage, search, and path-planning methods, several fundamental challenges remain, particularly for multi-agent systems operating in uncertain and dynamic environments.

One of the key challenges is scalability. As the number of agents increases, coordination complexity, communication overhead, and computational requirements grow significantly. Developing scalable algorithms that maintain efficiency and robustness while ensuring coordinated behavior remains an important research direction.

Another major challenge lies in improving robustness under uncertainty. Real-world environments are often characterized by incomplete, noisy, or time-varying information, which can significantly degrade performance. Future work should focus on methods that are resilient to uncertainties in sensing, communication, and environmental models, while maintaining reliable performance guarantees.

From a methodological perspective, there is a growing need to integrate different paradigms. Classical planning methods offer strong theoretical guarantees, while learning-based approaches provide adaptability and flexibility. Ergodic and coverage-based methods, on the other hand, incorporate spatial information distributions in a principled way. Combining these approaches into unified

frameworks represents a promising direction for achieving both theoretical rigor and practical effectiveness.

In addition, extending existing methods to heterogeneous multi-agent systems remains an open problem. Future systems will likely consist of agents with different sensing capabilities, dynamics, and roles, requiring more sophisticated coordination and resource allocation strategies.

Addressing these challenges will be essential for enabling the deployment of multi-agent search, path planning, and coverage methods in real-world applications characterized by uncertainty and dynamic conditions.

4 Conclusion

This paper provides a structured overview of path planning, search, and area coverage methods, emphasizing the strong interconnections between these problems and the common challenges they face in uncertain and dynamic environments. The reviewed approaches show that, although these problems are often studied separately, they are inherently related and frequently rely on similar underlying principles.

Despite significant progress, most existing methods remain predominantly focused on single-agent systems or rely on simplifying assumptions. As a result, efficient coordination of multiple agents in

unknown environments, particularly under limited communication and partial observability, remains a challenging and relatively underexplored problem.

Recent developments indicate a growing shift toward mathematically grounded frameworks that integrate path planning, search, and coverage within a unified perspective. Among these, ergodic approaches provide a particularly promising direction by explicitly incorporating spatial information distributions and enabling a natural balance between exploration and exploitation.

Overall, further advances in multi-agent systems will depend on the ability to combine theoretical rigor

with adaptability to yield scalable, robust, and efficient solutions for real-world autonomous systems operating in complex, dynamic environments.

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